

INDIA AND RUSSIA AS STRATEGIC PARTNERS

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Abstract

Russia and India are on the same page when it comes to constructing a new global relations architecture. These stances, which are based on the notion of a polycentric world structure, potentially open up new avenues for engagement between the two nations in a number of global and regional contexts. India and Russia agree that today's challenges can't be handled efficiently without a greater participation of emerging countries in international trade, banking, and investments. Developing nations have the potential to emerge and have to become the true engines of worldwide economic development.

Keywords: Bilateral Ties, Defence Cooperation, Strategic Partnership

Introduction

The erstwhile Soviet Union's cordial relationship with India, which began in the mid-1950s, was fueled by intertwined elements such as geopolitics, India's military and security concerns, and the two countries' shared ideology. The friendly and cohesive relationship between India and the Russian Federation (the successor state to the former Soviet Union) is founded not only on reciprocal economic, cultural, and political exchanges, but also on mutual perceptions of the world power structure and power balance. This paper would investigate the shifting features of Indo-Russian ties in light of current trends since the conclusion of the Cold War against the backdrop of a changing climate. First and foremost, it would examine significant changes in international relations. Second, it would briefly discuss the implications of strategic partnership on both countries' dimensions. Finally, it would examine the changing nuances of bilateral ties in the politico-strategic, economic, and defence realms.

Significant changes in international politics occurred during the post-Cold War period, which had a direct impact on the nature of state behaviour. Actors have started to redefine their roles and positions inside the systems. Bipolarity has vanished; favourable tendencies toward the establishment of a multipolar world are accelerating, and ties among key states, including former Cold War foes, are shifting.

Relations with New Delhi are described as a "special privileged strategic cooperation" in the July 2021 edition of Russia's National Security Strategy, which is discussed in the same paragraph as Russo-Chinese ties. Putin and Indian Prime Minister Narendra Modi have a great personal connection. Modi has expressed India's interest in economic ventures in Russia's Far East, effectively extending New Delhi's Look East policy to Vladivostok. Despite protests from Washington, India has proceeded with the acquisition of Russian-made S-400 air defence systems, which are expected to arrive by the end of the year. Modi is also one of just four foreign presidents to get the Order of St. Andrew, Russia's highest honour. Ordinary Russians regard India as a dependable friend with whom their own country has a trouble-free relationship. For their part, most Indians see Russia as a trusted ally who has never harmed India's strategic interests in its seventy-five years of independence.¹

However, problems are arising on a number of fronts, necessitating a rethinking, adjusting, and upgrading of the relationship by both the Indian and Russian leaderships to make it suitable for the twenty-first century. The major difficulty in world geopolitics is that Moscow and New Delhi, old friends and partners, are becoming increasingly tied to two opposing superpowers, China and the United

States. Furthermore, following the Himalayan border battles in 2020, India's relations with China, as well as Russia's with the US since the 2014 Ukraine crisis, can be characterised as confrontational. As a result, in a climate when their best friends are bonding with their worst adversaries, New Delhi and Moscow's major responsibility is to protect the Indo-Russia strategic cooperation from the larger and increasingly hostile global context while maintaining mutual confidence.ⁱⁱ

Strategic Partnership

Despite continued collaboration in sectors such as nuclear energy, outer space, and the Arctic, not to mention arms development and manufacture, the Indo-Russian relationship's evident weakness is its tiny and stagnating trading volumes. India, a fast-growing country, trades to the tune of \$100 billion with America and China—despite a tense political relationship with the latter—while trade with Russia remains at around \$10 billion. While 85 percent of India's GDP is now owned by private companies, Indo-Russian economic connections are still based on government-to-government accords. Trade volumes decreased once the previous model of Soviet-Indian economic cooperation collapsed in 1991. The Soviet Union used to be one of India's top three economic partners; the Russian Federation now ranks between between twentieth and twenty-fifth.ⁱⁱⁱ

Nonetheless, Russia retains its dominance in a few key areas, most notably military-technical collaboration. Arms industry has been a foundation of relations between the two countries since India's initial purchase of Mig-21 aircraft in 1962. However, India's growing determination to broaden its arms imports, as well as its recent announcement that it intends to design and manufacture armaments in-house, has resulted in a decline in Russia's position of the Indian arms market. As a result, Russia's share in the market has dwindled to slightly under 50%. Europe is becoming increasingly competitive, and the United States is becoming much more so.^{iv}

Despite their claims of a pivot to Asia, the present Russian elites are overwhelmingly Eurocentric and have very little time for India. China is considerably easier and more profitable to do business with for Russia's government-owned businesses and private business actors than India. Russian news organisations have a small presence in India and perform a poor job of describing Indian politics and policy to their consumers. The general people in Russia has a very limited comprehension of what is going on in India. In recent years, tourism and cultural exchanges have increased, but the pandemic has severely hampered them. After a promising start, an initiative to restart the practise of recruiting Indian students to study at Russian institutions has been hampered by COVID-related constraints.^v

India's elites, like Russia's, are Western-centric, but they are also Western-leaning, with a special concentration on the United States. Their goal is to become a member of the global elite. Russia is not a priority for them, and they have little interest in it. There are hardly no Russian reporters in the Indian media. Indian media editors typically rely on Western—mostly American and British—reporting and analysis, which is extremely critical of Russian policy, to cover Russia-related problems. Surprisingly, India's burgeoning IT sector has minimal ties to Russia and Russians.

Collaboration in Defence

In Hungary, India and Russia signed research and development agreements for the Rajasthan Atomic Power Station in 1961 (RAPS). In 1976, India and the Soviet Union signed a contract for the delivery of heavy waters. During the Cold War, Russia aided India by delivering fuel at Tarapur in 1982 and, after Pokhran-II, committed to assist in the construction of reactors and supply light water for reactors at Kundakulam in 1988. Despite some reservations, India has a strong defence relationship with Russia, since the guns have shown their worth, and the majority of our weapons are of Soviet provenance, which have gained widespread acceptance in Indian military circles. Russia is just around 10 years old as a

new country on the current political map of the world.^{vi}

It is, in fact, the Union of Soviet Socialist Republics' main successor state (USSR). Russia was awarded a permanent seat in the United Nations Security Council, which had previously been held by the Soviet Union until 1991. The fall of the Soviet Union was followed by two years of relative insecurity in India-Russia ties. Following that, India and Russia agreed to recast their relationship in light of the new realities produced by the post-Cold War era. Moscow has begun looking at the possibility of restarting Indo-Russian relations. While visiting India in January 1993, President Yeltsin replaced the previous 1971 pact with the new Treaty of Friendship and Cooperation.^{vii}

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Since 2007, the two have been cooperating on building a fifth-generation combat aircraft to strengthen defence relations. India has embarked on a massive defence modernisation programme as a result of the MIG-35. Apart from the accord, India inked a nuclear pact with Russia on November 7, 2009, marking a watershed point in bilateral relations. Both nations were in talks about building two or more nuclear power plants in Kundakulam. The Indian government recently announced the \$6 billion acquisition of five Russian S-400 supersonic air defence systems. The Kamov 226 helicopter will be built in India, according to the two parties. During the 13th annual conference, the two countries agreed on a joint civilian nuclear energy roadmap. From now until 2030, sixteen to eighteen nuclear reactors with a total installed capacity of 1000MW will be built. In keeping with the "Make in India" policy, India and Russia decided to increase their defence relationship. The 19th annual bilateral summit between India and Russia was held in September 2018 to further revitalise the partnership.

Conclusion

In the face of a changing regional and global security environment, it is evident that India-Russia ties are important for both nations. In recent years, India has worked to dispel the notion that it is leaning towards to the United States by focusing more on defence and energy partnerships. In the changing global context, India and Russia's connection must be cultivated. Both nations have always supported a rule-based international system, with both believing in a multipolar world. Compared to newer sources of defence supplies, Russia remains a major, as a result, energy presents a significant opportunity for mutually beneficial collaboration. India's globalised service sectors and corporations can aid Russian economic diversification and trade relations growth. India and Russia can't afford to squander their bilateral ties because they both rely on one another. As a result, they must coordinate their economic and geostrategic collaboration.

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